

EBFMC25-OP-04 · The Relationship Between Bone Mineral Density, Nutritional Habits, and Sun Exposure in Elderly

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: With the aging population, maintaining bone health has become a clinical priority due to the impact of metabolic bone diseases such as osteopenia and osteoporosis on morbidity and mortality (Xie et al., 2024; Yao et al., 2021). The decline in bone mineral density (BMD) increases the risk of fractures, reducing quality of life and imposing an additional burden on healthcare systems (de Jonge et al., 2018). This study aims to evaluate the relationship between daily dietary intake (milk, yogurt, cheese, coffee) and sun exposure duration with bone mineral density in individuals over 65 years of age.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted between September 2023 and December 2024. A total of 215 individuals over 65 years of age who visited the family medicine outpatient clinic of a tertiary hospital for any reason were included in the study. Participants completed a questionnaire prepared by the researchers, which collected demographic data, clinical history, and nutritional habits, followed by a dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DEXA) scan. Data analysis included descriptive statistics, the Mann-Whitney U test, and Spearman correlation analysis. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 72.27 ± 5.81 years, with 38.6% ($n=83$) being male and 61.4% ($n=132$) female. The mean T-scores were -0.57 ± 1.81 for the vertebrae and -1.22 ± 1.24 for the femur. Based on these values, 34.4% ($n=74$) of the participants were classified as normal, 45.1% ($n=97$) as osteopenic, and 20.5% ($n=44$) as osteoporotic. No significant association was found between daily consumption of milk ($p=0.135$), yogurt ($p=0.073$), or coffee ($p=0.241$) and T-scores. However, a significant positive correlation was observed between daily cheese consumption and T-scores ($p=0.034$). Furthermore, a statistically significant positive correlation was found between daily sun exposure duration and T-scores ($r=0.293$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Our study found a significant positive association between daily cheese consumption and bone mineral density in individuals over 65 years of age. However, no significant relationship was identified between the consumption of milk, yogurt, or coffee and BMD. Additionally, a positive correlation was observed between daily sun exposure duration and BMD. These findings suggest that cheese consumption and

adequate sun exposure may play a crucial role in the prevention of osteoporosis and osteopenia (Erkkilä et al., 2017; Kopiczko, 2020). Therefore, it is essential to enhance awareness programs targeting the nutritional and sun exposure habits of elderly individuals to maintain bone health.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Bone mineral density, osteoporosis, nutritional habits, sun exposure, DEXA

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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